

Riboflavin Sensitised Photooxidation of Indole-3-acetic Acid^ψ

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Manuscript received 4 August 1993, accepted 16 November 1993

The tendency of plants to bend towards light is called phototropism. It has been suggested that a flavin sensitised photooxidative destruction of indole-3-acetic acid (IAA), a plant growth hormone, takes place in the illuminated side of the plant¹. This retards the growth of the plant in the illuminated side in comparison to the dark side, thus causing the bending towards the light. However, whether the singlet^{2,3} or the triplet⁴ state of the flavin is involved in this phenomenon, has been the subject of a debate.

In this paper we report the results of a study on the aerobic photooxidation of IAA by riboflavin, and to assess the involvement of singlet and triplet states of riboflavin we have used a simple kinetic methodology which was discussed elsewhere⁵. We have used potassium iodide, potassium bromide and sodium azide, the three known quenchers of riboflavin singlet state, and have observed whether their inhibitory effect on the photooxidation rate matches their ability to quench the riboflavin singlet state, as expressed by their Stern-Volmer fluorescence quenching constants (K_{sv}) which are given by the Stern-Volmer equation.

$$F_0/F = 1 + K_{sv} [Q] \quad (1)$$

where [Q] is the quencher concentration, F_0 and F are fluorescence intensities in absence and presence of quencher respectively.

Aerobic photooxidation of IAA follows first

order mechanism and the reaction is kinetically slow. The kinetic rate constant is given by

$$k = \frac{C_0 - C}{C_0 t} \quad (2)$$

where C_0 is the initial concentration of IAA and C is the concentration of IAA after a photoreaction time t . The extent of inhibitory effect of quencher on the photooxidation was measured by the inhibition constant (K_{In}) which can be expressed by a similar equation⁵,

$$\frac{k_0}{k} = 1 + K_{In}[Q] \quad (3)$$

We have then plotted k_0/k versus quencher concentration. The slope of this plot gives K_{In} which is compared with K_{sv} the Stern-Volmer fluorescence quenching constant. If the K_{In} matches with K_{sv} , then the conclusion would be that the photoreaction involves mainly the singlet state of riboflavin, otherwise a reaction pathway through the riboflavin triplet state would be indicated.

Results and Discussion

The experimental results are depicted in Fig. 1. For potassium iodide as a quencher, we obtained a good linear plot. However, the slope is $453 M^{-1}$, much larger than the K_{sv} value of $60.5 M^{-1}$ at 37° . When Song and Metzler⁶ studied an aerobic photobleaching of riboflavin, they obtained a photoreaction inhibition constant of 173

^ψPresented at the 28th Annual Convention of Chemists at Calcutta, 1991.

Fig. 1. Comparison of the effects of several quenchers on riboflavin fluorescence and riboflavin sensitised photooxidation of indole-3-acetic acid: (●) fluorescence data and (○) photooxidation data.

M^{-1} against a K_{sv} value of $50 M^{-1}$ at 23–24°. This led them to assign a triplet mechanism for the reaction. As the difference in these two values is even larger in our study the case for a triplet mechanism is quite strong.

In the case of potassium bromide, we observed that the photoreaction rate remains almost same upto a potassium bromide concentration of 80 mM. Lasser and Feitelson on the basis of their flash photolysis studies found that upto a concentration of 0.1 M of potassium bromide, the

flavin triplet yield remains the same as the flavin triplet yield without any potassium bromide⁷. Since potassium bromide quenches the flavin singlet state from which the triplet state originates via intersystem crossing, they inferred that potassium bromide, by virtue of its external heavy atom effect, increases the intersystem crossing rate. Our results thus support the time-dependent triplet flash photolysis results.

Although iodine in potassium iodide is a heavier atom than bromine, the quenching power of potassium iodide of flavin triplet state is much larger than that of potassium bromide^{7,8}, thus the expected increase in intersystem crossing rate is not observed when potassium iodide is added. Also the flavin triplet quenching constant by potassium iodide is 322 times larger than that of by potassium bromide^{7,8}, whereas their Stern-Volmer fluorescence quenching constants are 60.5 and $35.5 M^{-1}$ respectively, a factor of only 1.7. Our K_{In} values for potassium iodide and potassium bromide are 453 and $2.1 M^{-1}$ (after a potassium bromide concentration of 40 mM) respectively, giving a ratio of 216, clearly suggesting a triplet mechanism for the photooxidation reaction.

With sodium azide as a quencher, the K_{In} and K_{sv} values are 80 and $50 M^{-1}$ respectively, giving further evidence against singlet mechanism. Here also we notice that upto a sodium azide concentration of 1 mM there is no inhibition of photoreaction. This is similar to the case of potassium bromide. Nitrogen (in azide) is not a heavy atom but azide may quench the excited states of riboflavin by electron-transfer mechanism.

In the light of the above experimental evidence, we therefore conclude that the photooxidation of IAA sensitised by riboflavin proceeds mainly through the riboflavin triplet state in vitro.

Experimental

Riboflavin (Sigma), indole-3-acetic acid (Glaxo), potassium iodide, potassium bromide (E. Merck) and sodium azide (Wilson Laboratories) were used

as received. Glass-distilled water was used for all the solutions. IAA concentration was monitored on a Perkin-Elmer MPF-44B spectrofluorometer equipped with a Julabo F20-UC (W. Germany) temperature controller, with excitation and emission wavelengths of 292 and 355 nm respectively. The solution for photochemistry contained before irradiation 2.2×10^{-4} M IAA, 1.8×10^{-5} M riboflavin, 0.1 M phosphate buffer of pH 5.7 and various amounts of different quenchers. The light source used for the photochemical experiments was a Phillips Comptalux 24V, 150 W tungsten spot-lamp situated 40 cm from the borosilicate glass reaction vessel. To cut off the heat generated by the lamp a 12 cm thick water filter was used. The temperature of the reaction mixture was kept constant at $37 \pm 1^\circ$ by a TWG (E. Germany) contact thermometer controlled circulatory water-bath. Water vapour saturated oxygen gas was bubbled through the reaction mixture during the photooxidation experiment. The irradiation time was 11 min. Riboflavin fluorescence quenching experiments were performed using air-equilibrated solutions at $37 \pm 1^\circ$ with excitation and emission wavelengths at 445 and 525 nm respectively. Riboflavin concentration used in the fluorescence experiments was 8.6×10^{-6} M.

Acknowledgement

Two of the authors (B.S. and U.D.) thank C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial support. The fluorescence measurements were performed at the Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, Calcutta.

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